

REVIEW ON THE USE OF CHEBYSHEV POLYNOMIALS FOR NUMERICAL MODELING OF APPLIED PROBLEMS

Djurayeva Nasiba Turakhanovna

Doctoral student of the Department of Applied
Mathematics of Termez State University
Termez State University, Uzbekistan
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Chebyshev polynomials are widely used for numerical modeling of various applied problems. The main advantage of methods using Chebyshev polynomials is the high speed of convergence of calculation results. If N - is the number of degrees of freedom (the number of Chebyshev polynomials or the number of nodes in a difference scheme), then when using difference methods the maximum error decreases as N^{-2} or N^{-4} (in difference methods of the second or fourth order of accuracy, respectively). However, in methods using Chebyshev polynomials, this error decreases at large N faster than N to any negative power. In difference methods, difference approximations are used to satisfy boundary conditions; in methods with Chebyshev polynomials, these conditions can be satisfied exactly. The use of Chebyshev polynomials in modeling the equation of diffusion and mass transfer arising in the food industry is described in [1]. In this work, polynomials are used to model the two-dimensional mass transfer equation occurring during convective air drying of food products. This modeling is used to improve the quality of dried food products and to predict moisture distribution.

To solve the problem of high-frequency stock price forecasting, paper [2] proposed a forecasting model based on Chebyshev stacking and weighted neural network. The proposed method extracts information about the characteristics of a function from a high-frequency series of stock prices through Chebyshev polynomial expansion.

Work [3] presents the development and research of a method for calculating transient processes in electrical circuits based on Chebyshev polynomials. Long-term electromagnetic transient processes occur in electrical systems due to switching and impulse effects, as a result of which the simulation time for such processes can be large, which is undesirable. The simulation time increases significantly if the circuit in the study is complex, and also if this circuit is described by a rigid system of equations of state. In this work, methods for calculating transient processes in electrical circuits based on the approximation

of solution functions by series using Chebyshev polynomials have been developed and studied.

A method for predicting stability during milling based on Chebyshev polynomials is given in [4]. The research carried out in this work relates to the field of modern production, in particular to the method of predicting stability during milling.

The general origin of the description of biological forms and special functions is the subject of study in [5]. Gilis transforms, originating from botany, are used to define square waves and Chebyshev polynomials.

The work [6] presents extremely reliable algorithms for solving density for multiparameter mixed models from the search for roots of the Chebyshev expansion. Calculation of mixture density for a given temperature, pressure and composition based on multi-parameter mixture models with Helmholtz energy sometimes fails; failures are caused by insufficiently accurate estimates of the density root, as well as insufficiently reliable numerical methods that may not converge to the desired density solution. Expansions in Chebyshev polynomials have the property that all roots of the expansion can be reliably obtained.

A modified multi-output feed-forward Chebyshev polynomial network for classifying wine regions by patterns is described in [7]. Based on existing results, this paper presents, analyzes and applies a modified multi-output feedforward Chebyshev polynomial neural network to classify vipodel region patterns.

Due to the intensive use of discrete transformations in image coding, the search for fast and energy-efficient approaches to their hardware implementation has become relevant. In [8], a new approximation for the integer discrete Chebyshev transform with better quality and energy efficiency due to the study of truncation and quality and energy efficiency due to the study of truncation and trimming is proposed. The basic idea is that reducing the coefficient values to fractions allows truncation by shifts in the internal transformation calculations and leads to smaller values of the non-diagonal remainders, which reduces non-orthogonality.

The work [9] presents a numerical simulation of a singularly perturbed fourth-order equation using the preliminary integration method. In this article, Chebyshev polynomials are used as basis functions in the pre-integration method. Tabular and graphical results show the high accuracy and efficiency of the proposed method.

The movement of an incompressible viscous fluid is described by the system of Navier-Stokes equations. From this system, the Orr-Sommerfeld

equation is obtained by the method of small perturbations, which is a fourth-order nonlinear ordinary differential equation with a small parameter at the highest derivative [10]. This article outlines methods for solving the eigenvalue problem for the Orr-Sommerfeld equation.

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